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Putting personality in context

17th european conference on personality

July 15 to July 19, 2014 – University of Lausanne, Switzerland

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Dear participants and colleagues,

On behalf of the European Association of Personality Psychology (EAPP), we are pleased to have our 17th European Conference on Personality held in Lausanne (Switzerland) from July 15th to July 19th 2014. I wish to thank the Chair, Prof. Jérôme Rossier, and the co-Chair, Dr. Marina Fiori, of the local organizing committee for their sustained effort in organizing what will surely be an excellent conference. My thanks extend to the other members of the organizing committee as well as the assistants, the local Tourist Office, and, in short, to everyone who has been instrumental and contributed to organizing the conference. It is the first time that an ECP is held in Switzerland as well as the first time in a French-speaking milieu. This can be an occasion for the EAPP and the ECP to expand its reach to relatively unchartered territories and increase the number and variety of its members, already totaling around 270 spread across many European and non-European countries. The variety and breadth of personality psychology is well reflected in this conference, with an exciting program of contributions covering the whole spectrum of specific topics related to personality psychology in its diverse ramifications. I'm sure that this will be a successful conference and wish you all a great time in Lausanne.

Marco Perugini
President of the EAPP

psychopathic traits from a developmental perspective, by examining (1) its evolution from childhood to adolescence, (2) to what extent early parenting predicts adolescent psychopathic traits, and (3) the presence of potential reciprocal effects. Data was collected in an initial sample (T1) of 192 children, aged 6 to 11, and then reassessed in a follow-up conducted six years later (T2, n = 138). Results highlight the influence of parenting practices based on affection and warmth, showing some distinctive associations in childhood and adolescence, and evidencing the existence of bidirectional dynamics between psychopathic traits and parenting. These findings support previous results, and provide new and useful evidences in terms of prevention and intervention practices.

PO2.63 Longitudinal study on development of personality traits measured by Picture Based Personality Survey. Preliminary results

Marta MACKIEWICZ, *University of Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński in Warsaw, Poland*

Jan CIECIUCH, *University of Finance and Management, Poland; University of Zurich, Switzerland*

The Picture Based Personality Survey for Children (PBPS-C) is a method for measuring personality traits based on the Big Five Model. The main idea of PBPS-C is that the personality traits are indicated by pictures presenting behaviors. Primary aim of current study was to explore longitudinal change in traits, taking into account gender differences. The total sample comprised of 1110 children aged between 6 and 13 years old. The personality traits were measured three times with 6 months distance. As the preliminary analysis we have conducted multigroup confirmatory factor analysis across gender and measurement points in order to establish the measurement invariance. We have distinguished three levels of measurement invariance: configural, metric and scalar. In the main analysis we have used latent growth modeling that allows to assess the longitudinal change. Gender was introduced into the model as variable that can explain slope of change. During the presentation we will present our findings and discuss them in light of developmental processes in childhood.

PO2.64 Task completion time on the Trail Making Test-A: Interaction effects of rRST dimensions and age

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The principal aim of the study was to examine the relations between task completion time on the Trail Making Test, series A (TMT-A), general intelligence, personality traits, age and gender, with the emphasis on interactions between personality traits and age. The sample comprised 251 participants (51% female), aged 18 - 70. Besides the TMT, The Reinforcement Sensitivity Questionnaire was applied as a measure of constructs of the revised Gray's model, while intelligence was measured by the Advanced Raven's Progressive matrices. The results of hierarchical multiple regression revealed significant

partial contributions of age (Beta = .31, $p = .00$), intelligence (Beta = -.21, $p = .00$), as well as interactions age - BIS (Beta = -.20, $p = .02$), age - BAS (Beta = .14, $p = .03$), and age - Flight (Beta = .20, $p = .00$). In older participants, TMT task completion time is negatively related to BIS, and positively to BAS and Flight.

PO2.65 Domain-specific creativity in relation to the autism spectrum characteristics

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The study was aimed to examine domain-specific creativity in relation to the autism spectrum characteristics, including social skills, imagination, attention switching, communication, and attention to detail. The research sample consisted of 1112 university students who were administrated Baron-Cohen's Autism Spectrum Quotient (AQ), Kaufman's Domains of Creativity Scale (K-DOCS), and Carson's Creative Achievement Questionnaire (CAQ). The results suggest that higher AQ scores negatively correlate with creativity in everyday life, sense of humour, and performance creativity encompassing music, writing and public presentation. There were also found some significant gender differences in creative interests and autistic features.

PO2.66 Does birth order affect personality? An analysis of three national samples

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Boris EGLOFF, *Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Germany*

Stefan C. SCHMUKLE, *University of Leipzig, Germany*

Despite strong theoretical claims (e.g. Sulloway, 1996), research on the impact of birth order on personality has led to inconsistent results. However, as the sample sizes of these studies were much smaller than those examining effects on intelligence and probably too small in view of the to-be-expected effect sizes, further research is needed. Here we analyze large national panels from Great Britain ($N > 4,000$), the USA ($N > 5,000$), and Germany (anticipated $N = 20,000$) for effects of birth order position on personality and intelligence. We conducted separate analyses for families with different numbers of siblings to rule out potential confounds associated with family size. For the British and American samples we replicated the previously reported small but significant decline of intelligence from firstborns to laterborns, but we did not find any effects on the Big Five personality traits. Data of the German sample will be presented at the conference.